

Glutamate Dehydrogenase and the Changing Pattern of Excretory Ammonia and Urea in *Heteropneustes fossilis*

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Abstract : Fishes, in general, follow ammonotelic mode of excretion. However, certain stress factors may provoke them to excrete urea. In the present study, the possible role of ureogenesis to avoid accumulation of toxic ammonia under water-restricted condition was tested in *Heteropneustes fossilis*. A total of hundred fishes were collected and sacrificed. Excretory urea and ammonia were estimated in the water of the aquarium and glutamate dehydrogenase activity was measured in the hepatic tissue. During the experimental period, excretory ammonia in *Heteropneustes fossilis* was found between 931% to 16% above the baseline ammonia and excretory urea was found between 112% to 898% above the baseline urea. A high degree of correlation with r (coefficient of correlation) above 0.9 is observed between excretory ammonia and urea in *Heteropneustes fossilis*. However, only a moderate degree of correlation is observed between the activity of glutamate dehydrogenase and excretory ammonia and urea.

Keywords : ammonia, aquarium, glutamate dehydrogenase, urea, ureogenesis

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